

ADDRESSING THE DATA SCARCITY OF TAMIL: A ZERO-SHOT COREFERENCE RESOLUTION APPROACH WITH MURIL

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ABSTRACT

Coreference resolution which establishes whether different kind of expressions in a text relate to the same thing, is an essential part of natural language understanding. Although this task has seen substantial development in high-resource languages, particularly through the use of large annotated datasets and pretrained models development. Languages like Tamil under explored because of the limited annotated datasets and specialized language models. To overcome this, a zero-shot method for coreference resolution in Tamil by (MuRIL,) a multilingual pretrained language model is proposed. The framework adapts span-based neural architectures, using contextual span representations, cosine similarity-based scoring, and unsupervised agglomerative clustering to detect and link coreferent mentions efficiently. To facilitate evaluation, a new manually annotated dataset, TGAP (Tamil GAP-style Coreference Dataset) was developed drawn from diverse text sources. Experimental evaluation compared MuRIL with other multilingual baselines using standard metrics such as MUC, B³, CEAF, and LEA F1 scores. Results shows that MuRIL gives the highest overall F1 score (0.67), performing well with other models underscoring the value of language-specific pretraining. The findings shows that a zero-shot, annotation-free framework can achieve competitive performance for Tamil coreference resolution.

Keywords: *Coreference Resolution, Tamil language, Multilingual language model, Zero Shot Learning, Span based Embedding*

1. INTRODUCTION

Coreference resolution is a fundamental task in various downstream applications, including information extraction [1], machine translation [2], question answering [3], and text simplification [4]. Although coreference resolution has seen progressed in high-resource languages like English, many low-resource languages, such as Tamil, remain underserved due to the lack of linguistic data resources and annotated datasets [5]. With its rich morphology, free word order, and implicit pronouns, Tamil is one of the classical Indian languages spoken by more than 70 million people, and presents particular linguistic difficulties for coreference resolution [6]. These characteristics make standard approaches developed for English less effective when directly applied to Tamil. Therefore, Language-specific strategies and the development of Tamil coreference annotated

corpora are necessary. The scarcity of annotated corpora such as OntoNotes [7], CoNLL-2012 [8], and GAP [9] in Tamil has made supervised learning approaches infeasible.

Table 1: Sample Sentences For Coreference Resolution In Tamil

Original Sentence	Coreference
(Tanglish) Ravi palliki sendaar. Avar mugavum puthisali Ravi went to school. He is very intelligent.	Coreference: Avar(He) "Ravi"
Mala puthagam vanginaal. Athu mugavum suvarasyamanathu. Mala bought a book. It is very interesting.	Coreference: "Athu (It) Puththagam (book)"
Amar and Anu poongavirku sendranar. Avargal angu vilaiyaddinar. Amar and Anu went to the park. They played there.	Coreference: Avargal (They) - (Amar and Anu)

The sample coreference resolution in Tamil is tabulated in Table 1. Because of their diverse scripts and grammatical structures, indigenous languages present unique challenges for the application of current coreference resolution models [10]. Transformer architecture based models, such as Bert [9], SpanBert [16], have revolutionized coreference resolution for high resource languages. However, their applicability to low resource and morphologically complex languages like Tamil remains limited and The span based similarity calculation has not been fully investigated in earlier research. So Investing Zero-shot coreference resolution methods that can make use of multilingual transformer representations without relying on task specific tamil annotations is important one.

1.1 Problem Definition

Low-resource languages like Tamil continue to face challenges due to a lack of annotated corpora, inadequate linguistic resources, and the unavailability of specialized tools, despite notable progress in coreference resolution for high-resource languages like English using transformer architectures. Due to their primary training and fine-tuning on English-focused datasets, current multilingual coreference models often show poor generalization in Tamil, leading to disparities between language and domain. Moreover, the development of supervised models for Tamil is challenging due to the absence of large, manually annotated datasets required for neural architectures. The development of resource-efficient, language-neutral frameworks that can use cross-lingual knowledge without the need for Tamil-specific annotations or fine-tuning. To address this gap, the proposed work suggests a zero-shot coreference resolution method using MuRIL, a multilingual transformer trained on Indian languages. This approach eliminates the need for Tamil-specific training by modifying span-based coreference frameworks and utilizing cosine similarity between contextual span embeddings.

The Research Objectives are:

1. To develop a zero-shot coreference resolution framework for the Tamil language by using MuRIL a transformer-based multilingual language model for several Indian languages that eliminating the need for task-specific annotated data.
2. The proposed framework uses span-based neural architectures by using contextual span representations, cosine similarity-based

scoring, and unsupervised agglomerative clustering to identify and link coreferent mentions efficiently.

3. A custom TGAP dataset is developed to validate the model that specifically captures the linguistic characteristics and coreference patterns unique to the Tamil language.

The research objectives are discussed in the methodology section and the research questions discussed in the discussion section are as follows:
 RQ1: What architectural adaptations are necessary to enable zero-shot coreference resolution for morphologically complex languages like Tamil?
 RQ2 : What impact does span based similarity computation have on the precision and effectiveness of Tamil Zero shot coreference resolution?

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Coreference Resolution in High Resource Languages

In the early research, mention-pair models [13] were primarily used ,which, despite their simplicity, were limited by their inability to capture document-level coherence. In order to address this weakness, mention-ranking and entity-level models [14] have been introduced, which include broader contextual information across mentions. Subsequently, neural models with end-to-end span-ranking [15] marked an advancement by jointly modeling mentions and antecedents, which eliminated the dependency on predefined mention boundaries. The inclusion of contextualized embeddings such as ELMo, BERT, and SpanBERT [16] further improved performance by enriching semantic representation. These methods still require massive annotated corpora and computational resources, rendering them impracticable for low-resource languages. On the other hand, generative approaches [17] cast coreference as a text generation task, offering conceptual novelty at an increased computational cost. Maverick [18] alleviated this by proposing an encoder-only framework that achieved competitive accuracy with reduced computational complexity and demonstrated that architectural efficiency can rival data-intensive generative systems. Nevertheless, most of these recent innovations are designed around English, with limited cross-lingual transferability or adaptability to low-resource languages.

2.2 Coreference Resolution in South Asian Languages

Research in South Asian languages is relatively limited because of the scarcity of available data and its rich linguistic morphology. A multilingual pre-trained transformer model, such as mBERT [19], and XLM-R [20], provides cross-lingual coreference, giving a certain degree of transfer from high-resource languages. However, these models usually ignore the morphologically richest side of Indian languages, which often results in suboptimal performance in downstream tasks. To alleviate this issue, MuRIL [21] has been specifically designed for several Indian languages, enhancing cross-script representation and tokenization. Its application to coreference resolution, however, for Tamil, remains less explored. In recent times, various efforts, such as CorefUD [22] and TransMuCoRes [23], have tried to bridge the resource gap using translated corpora. However, these approaches fail to preserve the cultural and linguistic richness, which is an indispensable part of regional languages.

Bridge the GAP [24] represented an important step toward pronominal disambiguation using multilingual models and zero-shot transfer, focusing on the need for culturally informed pretraining. Similarly, end-to-end multilingual frameworks have been presented in [25]. have shown that joint learning across related languages improves generalization but still struggle with language-specific phenomena like noun-to-noun anaphora in Tamil. [26] Proposed scalable mechanisms by models for scenarios based on peer-to-peer networks in low-resource situations are limited by empirical results related to Dravidian languages. Recent works, [27] have investigated paragraph alignment across Dravidian languages, marking one step toward richer cross-lingual representations. Building on this, [28] subsequent work has extended these efforts to question answering tasks in Indic languages, reflecting a growing emphasis on context-aware understanding and multilingual knowledge transfer.

For Tamil in particular, [29] addressed noun-to-noun anaphora, which showed that entity reference poses some unique morphological and syntactic challenges. [30] presented a modular anaphora resolution engine, incorporating linguistic features of Dravidian languages, which facilitates cross-lingual robustness. DeepHCoref [31] further investigated zero-shot and few-resource scenarios with respect to Tamil and Hindi, and although the feasibility could be demonstrated, no thorough

evaluation was provided regarding Tamil-specific phenomena like span-based contextual similarity.

Overall, while multilingual and cross-lingual efforts have advanced the state of South Asian NLP, there remains a critical gap in Tamil coreference resolution research. Most models are (i) depend on annotated corpora, (ii) underperform on morphologically complex structures, or (iii) fail to model contextual similarity beyond sentence boundaries. This motivates the need for a zero-shot, multilingual framework for Tamil that can effectively resolve pronouns and named entities without supervised data, balancing accuracy, efficiency, and linguistic generalization. Our approach adapts span-based coreference architectures originally designed for English that involves contextual span representations, similarity-based scoring, and unsupervised clustering to derive final coreference clusters without any Tamil-specific fine-tuning.

3. TGAP Dataset

To facilitate evaluation and development of Tamil coreference resolution systems, we constructed TGAP, a manually annotated dataset tailored for both pronominal and semantic coreference tasks.

Table 2: TGAP Dataset Features

Features	Value
Sentences	3,000
PronounCoreference Instances	3,000
SemanticCoreference Instances	550
Total Coreference Pairs	3,550
Pronouns Covered	avan, aval, avar, avargal, athu, athai, ivar, ival, ivan, ivai, avai (he, she, it, his, her, they, them)

The design of TGAP follows the framework of prior GAP-style datasets but uses linguistic adaptations specific to Tamil morphology and syntax. The TGAP dataset consists of 3,000 sentences with manually annotated pronoun-based coreference instances and 550 semantic coreference pairs. Sentences were created from diverse textual sources with lexical richness and contextual variety. Each entry includes:

A target pronoun (e.g., avan – he, aval – she, athu – it), Two candidate antecedents (A and B), Character offsets for all spans, Binary coreference labels

indicating whether the pronoun refers to A or B. In addition to pronominal examples, TGAP includes semantically motivated coreference links are Appositive expressions and nominal references. For example: (Munal janathipathi (Former President) = Abdulkalam), Nominal references (Example Vilangu (animal) = Singam (lion)).

TGAP uses a GAP-style tabular format that containing fields like Text, Pronoun, Pronoun-offset, A, A-offset, A-coref, B, B-offset, and B-coref. For semantic relations, the fields Mention1 and Mention2 replace A and B, with an additional Type field labeled as “semantic”. While modest in size compared to large English corpora, TGAP represents a substantial and high-quality resource for Tamil, a low-resource language. Its manually verified annotations and inclusion of both pronominal and semantic relations. The dataset demonstrates that meaningful progress is achievable even with limited annotated data which especially when supported by cross-lingual transfer and model efficiency.

4. METHODOLOGY

This work proposes a zero shot coreference resolution framework by MuRIL, a multilingual transformer based model which is trained on Indian languages. The proposed model introduces a efficient span-based mention detection and cosine similarity-based span clustering mechanism to identify and link coreferent mentions efficiently in Tamil. First, the model process, span-based mention detection method, which extracting candidate spans that represent potential entity mentions across the text. Each span is then encoded by using contextual embeddings derived from MuRIL, which capture rich semantic and syntactic distinctions specific to Tamil’s morphology. To establish coreferent links among these spans, the model adapts a cosine similarity-based scoring mechanism that measures semantic relatedness between span representations. This approach fundamentally departs from traditional mention-pair and span-ranking architectures, which depend on dense neural scoring layers and large parameter sets which making them computationally expensive and less adaptable to low-resource environments. Instead, by using pairwise cosine similarity between span embeddings, the model achieves unsupervised semantic alignment process without the need of task-specific training or fine-tuning. The resulting similarity matrix is processed by using an agglomerative clustering algorithm that automatically groups spans referring to the same

real-world entity. This integrated framework, which combines span-based mention detection with similarity-driven clustering reduces computational overhead while preserving interpretability, scalability, and various domains applicability. Our technique determines coreference connections by calculating cosine similarity between pronouns and potential antecedents eliminating the need for task-specific training. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed system inspired by span-based neural coreference models such as SpanBERT. The architecture comprises into following stages: encoding, span candidate generation, embedding construction and scoring and clustering.

Figure 1 Architecture Of The Proposed Work

4.1 Encoding with MuRIL

MuRIL (Multilingual Representations for Indian Languages), a transformer based model pretrained on a varied multilingual corpus of Indian languages including Tamil. The system's first stage to encode the input text. The model uses SentencePiece to tokenize sub words in a given Tamil phrase or paragraph before feeding the tokenized sequence into the MuRIL encoder. In Eq (1) process as defined:

$$H = \text{MURIL}(X) = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_n\} \text{-----} (1)$$

where d is the hidden size of MURIL and $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the embedding of the i th token. These embeddings are the basis for recognizing and contrasting coreferent spans in subsequent phases by encapsulating syntactic, semantic and positional information.

4.2 Span Candidate Generation

After encoding, we use the tokenized sequence to produce an extensive collection of span possibilities. Any consecutive subsequence of tokens that falls inside a given maximum width is referred to as a span. At the expense of more computation which we subsequently address by pruning, this approach guarantees strong recall of possible coreference mentions. We compute the mean pooled embedding for each candidate span by averaging the contextual embeddings of the constituent tokens. The fixed-length vector generated by this procedure represents the semantic content of the span within its surrounding context. These span-level representations are employed in clustering and similarity calculations. This design guarantees high recall of possible coreference mentions, trading off for more computation, which we subsequently tackle through pruning. For every candidate span, we calculate a mean-pooled embedding by averaging the contextual embeddings of its constituent tokens. This process produces a vector of constant length that gives the semantic meaning of the span within its contextual representations. These span-level representations are used for similarity calculations and categorization. Then we create an extensive array of span candidates from the tokenized sequence. A span is described as any uninterrupted subsequence of tokens within a given maximum width.

$$A = \pi\{(i,j) | 1 \leq i \leq j \leq n, j - i + 1 \leq wmax\} \dots (2)$$

Equation (2) allows the model to capture a wide range of linguistic units including Pronouns, Noun phrases, Named entities.

4.3 Span Embedding via Mean Pooling

For every candidate span, we calculate a mean-pooled embedding by averaging the contextual embeddings of its constituent tokens. It produces a fixed length vector that provides the semantic meaning of the span for its surrounding context. These span-level representations are employed in similarity computation and clustering. The mean-pooled embedding vector for each span $s = (i, j)$ is calculated by averaging the contextual token embeddings inside the span:

$$V_s = \frac{1}{j-i+1} \sum_{k=i}^j h_k \dots (3)$$

In Eq (3) gives the semantic identity of the span in its context.

4.4 Span Scoring and Pruning

To reduce noise and computational complexity, we apply a span scoring function to rank candidates. However, in this zero-shot setting, we rely on heuristic pruning, discarding spans containing function words or low-information content. The top-K ranked mentions are retained for further processing. To ease computational burden and improve precision that we apply a span filtering strategy that removes unlikely or low-value candidates. While supervised models employ learned mention scoring functions, our zero-shot framework demonstrates heuristic pruning which includes: Length filtering (Retain spans up to a fixed width). Function word exclusion (Discard spans that primarily contain stop words or punctuation). It reduces the number of span comparisons in upcoming stages and focuses on mentions.

4.5 Similarity Computation

For every pair of retained spans (s_i, s_j) (s_i, s_j) to compute their cosine similarity to assess the likelihood of coreference defined in Eq(4):

$$Sim(s_i, s_j) = \frac{v_{s_i} \cdot v_{s_j}}{\|v_{s_i}\| \|v_{s_j}\|} \dots (4)$$

High similarity values provide that the two spans represent the same real-world entity. This pairwise similarity matrix serves as the affinity input to the clustering stage.

4.6 Agglomerative Clustering

To identify coreference chains, we perform agglomerative hierarchical clustering on the span similarity matrix. The algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Select every span as a singleton cluster.
2. Then, recursively merge the most similar cluster pair if their similarity is above the threshold.
3. Continue until no pair exceeds the threshold for similarity.

This unsupervised clustering strategy produces coreference clusters, where each cluster contains mentions referring to the same entity. Unlike graph based or classifier based resolution models, this method is parameter-free and entirely dependent on the quality of contextual span representations. The cosine similarity matrix is input to an agglomerative clustering algorithm, which iteratively merges span pairs into clusters based on

their similarity. Each resulting cluster is interpreted as a coreference chain spans.

5. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The proposed zero-shot coreference resolution framework for Tamil was implemented using the MuRIL (Multilingual Representations for Indian Languages) transformer-based model, which is pre-trained on a number of multilingual corpora for 17 Indian languages, including Tamil, and it adapts the span-based neural architecture typically used in English coreference models to a zero-shot setting that does not require Tamil-specific annotated data. The input text is then tokenized using the SentencePiece tokenizer compatible with MuRIL, followed by the generation of contextualized embeddings for each token, which uses semantic and syntactic information across multilingual contexts to identify possible mention spans. Finally, it generates candidate spans, which are potential mention spans or entity references in a sentence. Span embeddings are fixed-length vectors that represent the contextual semantics of spans, obtained by mean pooling over the token embeddings in the span, followed by span pruning using heuristic rules such as span length, function word exclusion, and frequency-based filtering, and finally, cosine similarity between remaining span pairs to determine a similarity matrix that is input to an agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm that merges span pairs with similarity above a threshold, resulting in coherent coreference chains without task-specific supervision. The entire framework is implemented in PyTorch libraries, with matrix computations optimized via GPU acceleration. This design allows the model to perform effective zero-shot inference for Tamil coreference resolution while keeping computational feasibility for larger multilingual applications.

6. EVALUATION METRICS

The evaluation of various transformer-based models for coreference resolution in Tamil utilized standard metrics in addition to coreference-specific metrics such as MUC F1, B³ F1, CEAF F1, and LEA F1. Table 3 displays the comparative effectiveness of each model regarding coreference resolution in Tamil. Among the models, MuRIL shows the overall better performance which achieving an F1 score of 0.67 and notable results in MUC F1 (67.42), B³ F1 (70.18), CEAF F1 (66.85), and LEA F1 (71.86) demonstrating its capability in creating coherent and accurate coreference clusters. On the other hand, mBERT performed reasonably well (F1 = 0.59), although it did not achieve the best performance, indicating that although the multilingual pretraining helped, it was not enough to capture the fine-grained anaphoric relationships in Tamil.

However, the relatively good performance of mBERT implies that general-purpose multilingual transformers can transfer some contextual knowledge across typologically similar languages. Models like XLM-R and IndicBERT with F1 scores in the range of 0.40, showing that they are not especially useful for zero-shot coreference resolution in Tamil. Although XLM-R was trained extensively on a large corpus of languages, it did not capture the structural properties of Tamil, such as case marking and postpositional patterns, and IndicBERT, designed for Indian languages, did not model entity-level coherence over long spans. MuRIL takes advantage of the balanced representation of Indian scripts, vocabulary coverage, and syntactic alignment across related languages that leads to high-quality span embeddings suitable for zero-shot inference.

Table 3: Comparison Of Models On Tamil Coreference Resolution

Model	Accu-racy	Precisi-on	Re call	F1 Score	MUC F1	B ³ F1	CEAF F1	LEA F1
MuRIL	0.650	0.69	0.65	0.67	67.42	70.18	66.85	71.86
mBERT	0.600	0.60	0.59	0.59	60.10	61.80	59.00	62.50
XLM-R	0.400	0.42	0.40	0.41	48.65	52.31	50.24	54.70
Indic BERT	0.400	0.41	0.39	0.40	46.70	50.20	48.10	52.00

Figure 2: Model Comparison On Tamil Coreference Resolution

7. RESULTS

We applied it to a TGAP dataset containing 2,000 sentences. A collection of representative instances is displayed in Table 4 and Table 5 demonstrating the model's capability to accurately link pronouns to their respective antecedents.

Table 4: Sample Sentences predicted by Muril Bert Base Model for Coreference Resolution in tamil

Sentence	Pronoun	Gold Coref	Predicted Coref
(Tanglish): Anu pallikku Sendraar, yenneynil aval aasiriyarai sandhikka virumbinaal. Anu went to school because she wanted to meet the teacher.	Aval (She)	Anu	Anu
(Tanglish): Ameer noolagathil irundhaar. Avar ange oru puthagam vaasithhaar. Ameer was in the library. He read a book there.	Avar (He)	Ameer	Ameer
(Tanglish): Seetha matrum Ramya pallikku sendaargal. Aval puthagam kondu vanthaal. Seetha and Ramya went to school. She brought book.	Aval (She)	Seetha	Ramya
Maanavargal vakupparaial irundhaargal. Avargal aasiriyaraik kettaargal. The students were in the classroom. They listened to the teacher.	Avargal (They)	Maanavargal(Students)	Maanavargal(Students)

Table 5: Sample sentences for both semantic and pronominal

Sentence	Mention	Referent	Type
Surya oru nalla nadigar. Avar pala hit padangalil nadiththullaar. Surya is a good actor. He has acted in many hit movies.	Avar(He)	Surya	Pronominal
Disney Films migavum pirabalaamaanathu. Indha niruvanam kuzhandhaigal virumbum kathaigalai uruvaakkugiradhu. Disney Films is very popular. This company creates stories that children love.	Intha niruvanam (This Company)	Disney Films	Nominal
Rajinikanth oru superstar. Indha nadigar pala thalaimuraigalai eerththullaar. Rajinikanth is a superstar. This actor has inspired many generations.	Intha nadigar(This Actor)	Rajinikanth	Semantic

These sentences gives semantic coreference, where the coreferent is referenced through conceptual or descriptive terms (e.g., “Intha nadigar” = this actor).Resolving such terms often requires world knowledge and ontological understanding. In the above example “Rajinikanth” is an actor refers to a

nominal coreference, where an entity is referenced again by using a descriptive noun.

8. DISCUSSION

This section answers the two research questions posed in the introduction section. For

RQ1, the results showed that zero-shot coreference resolution for a morphologically complex and low-resource language like Tamil needs architectural changes such as a multilingual encoder trained on Indian languages, such as MuRIL, to capture Tamil morphological and syntactic patterns which representing mentions at the span level rather than the token level was particularly beneficial since span embeddings capture more contextual and semantic information needed to resolve noun phrases and pronouns in an agglutinative language like Tamil and heuristic span pruning was useful to strike a balance between computational efficiency and precision by removing low-value spans while retaining high-value candidates. The cosine similarity-based scoring combined with unsupervised agglomerative clustering was also found to be effective in linking coreferent mentions without the requirement of task-specific training data. These adaptations together address the issues of free word order, morphological richness, and lack of annotated resources for Tamil. RQ2: The span-based similarity computation had impact on both the accuracy and overall performance of the model. It showed improved precision in identifying the correct pronoun-antecedent relationships. However, recall decreased moderately due to the precision-recall trade-off caused by aggressive pruning and conservative clustering thresholds.

However, the overall F1 performance of MuRIL (0.67) was still higher than other multilingual baselines such as mBERT and XLM-R, showing the effectiveness of span-based similarity in a zero-shot setup. The results suggest that similarity thresholding is a critical factor and that small adjustments to it can impact model performance for adaptive or learned thresholding mechanisms in future work. Span-based similarity computation, when combined with Tamil-aware multilingual embeddings and efficient clustering presents a promising and scalable solution for zero-shot coreference resolution in low-resource languages.

9. CONCLUSION

Coreference resolution, which refers to the task of resolving coreferent words and phrases in natural language is a challenging problem for morphologically complex and low-resource languages like Tamil. This research presents a zero-shot coreference resolution framework that does not require task-specific annotated corpora and relies on the MuRIL multilingual transformer model trained on Indian languages by integrating span-

based contextual representations, cosine similarity-based scoring, and unsupervised agglomerative clustering to identify and link coreferent mentions in Tamil text without fine-tuning. The experimental results show that MuRIL performed better than other multilingual baselines, such as mBERT[19], XLM-R[20], and IndicBERT, on all evaluation metrics, with an overall F1 score of 0.67, which indicates the importance of language-specific pretraining and context-aware span representation in improving zero-shot performance for Tamil. Develop the TGAP dataset, a manually annotated Tamil GAP-style corpus, which can be used as a resource for future research in South Asian NLP. This work follows three scientific contributions: It proposes the first zero-shot Tamil coreference resolution framework that does not depend on annotated training data, which advancing research in low-resource language understanding. It specifically validates the effectiveness of span-based similarity computation within a multilingual zero-shot setting, that bridging a gap between high-resource and low-resource adaptation. It provides the TGAP dataset for systematic evaluation and reproducibility in Tamil coreference studies.

However, some of the limitations: (1) the use of cosine similarity and heuristic pruning may limit the model's ability to capture more exact semantic relationships and contextual disambiguation; (2) although MuRIL was pretrained on Indian languages, some Tamil-specific dialectal variations may not be fully represented; (3) the evaluation is limited by the relatively small size of the TGAP dataset; expanding the dataset to cover a broader range of domains and genres would strengthen robustness and generalization; and (4) the current framework does not include discourse-level or cross-sentence reasoning, which could improve performance in more complex text scenarios. Future work could also investigate hybrid semi-supervised methods and cross-lingual transfer learning to address these limitations. The model could be extended to other Dravidian languages and integrated into multilingual LLMs.

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